

SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND APPLICATIONS IIMT UNIVERSITY, MEERUT, UTTAR PRADESH, INDIA

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON ADVANCE IN COMPUTING COMMUNICATION AND CONTROL ICA3C : 2020, (16Th- 17Th JUNE , 2020)

This is to certify that

(Prof./Dr./Mr./Ms.) **Pillalamarri Laxman**

ECE DEPARTMENT ,ST MARTINS ENGINEERING COLLEGE ,RESEARCH SCHOLAR @ LOVELY PROFESSIONAL UNIVERSITY.

has participated and presented paper entitled “ ***A Survey on Design And Performance Evaluation Of Drown Death Prevention Systems-EMBEDDED & IoT*** ” in Online International Conference on Advances in Computing, Communication and Control” (ICA3C-2020) on 16/06/2020, organised by School of Computer Science and Applications, IIMT University, Meerut, Uttar Pradesh, INDIA.

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